

Synthesis, characterization and application of cellulose nitrilotriacetic acid (CNTAA) resin for removal of heavy metal ions from industrial effluent

A. V. Singh* and Rakesh Singh

Department of Chemistry, Jai Narain Vyas University, Jodhpur-342 033, Rajasthan, India

E-mail : areshvikram04@rediffmail.com

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Abstract : A new cellulose based resin containing nitrilotriacetic acid group was synthesized. The nitrilotriacetic acid group has been incorporated onto cellulose by a modified Porath's method of functionalisation of polysaccharides. Cellulose nitrilotriacetic acid (CNTAA) resin can selectively separate heavy metal ions from industrial effluent. The CNTAA resin was characterized by FTIR, thermogravimetric analysis. The distribution coefficient (K_d) of metal ions at different pH was studied using batch equilibration method. The effects of pH, agitation speed, treatment time, flow rate, contact time, temperature and adsorbent dose, on the removal of metal ions from industrial effluent were investigated. The resin is amenable for continuous process and can be regenerated several times. The adsorption of different metal ions on CNTAA resin follows the order : $\text{Fe}^{\text{II}} > \text{Zn}^{\text{II}} > \text{Cu}^{\text{II}} > \text{Cd}^{\text{II}} > \text{Pb}^{\text{II}}$.

Keywords : Cellulose nitrilotriacetic acid resin, distribution coefficient, thermogravimetric analysis.

Introduction

The pollution of the environment with heavy metals is a result of many human activities, such as mining and metallurgy which adversely affect the ecosystem. In view of this, the need of developing technologies that can not only cleanup but also recover valuable components from industrial effluent. The removal of heavy metal ions from industrial effluent can be achieved by several processes, such as precipitation¹, solvent extraction^{2,3}, chemical and electrochemical technique⁴ and advanced oxidation process^{5,6}. Most of these processes may be ineffective, extremely expensive or generate secondary pollution. In recent years, the adsorption of metal ion by ion exchange method⁷⁻¹⁴ has received much attention and becomes one of the most popular method because of its competitive and effective process for the removal of heavy metal ions from industrial effluent.

Many studies have shown the functionalization of a polysaccharide matrix with different chelating functionalities for heavy metal ions removal from industrial effluent and wastewater¹⁵⁻²⁵. The adsorption of heavy metal ions using chelating ion exchange resins is a green analytical method since it does not involve the use of toxic chlorinated organic solvents, which are very fre-

quently used in conventional liquid-liquid extraction technique or other methods²⁶. The main objective of the most of the research works on chelating resins is preparation of insoluble functionalized polymers which can provide more flexible working conditions together with good stability and high capacity for certain metal ions. The interest in this type of chelating resins are due to the rapid adsorption of metal ions, higher selectivity and less swelling, in comparison with the analogous organic polymers²⁷.

Cellulose is an organic compound with the formula $(\text{C}_6\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_5)_n$, a polysaccharide consisting of a linear chain of several hundred units²⁸. Cellulose is straight chain polymer, which contained D-glucose units with $\beta(1 \rightarrow 4)$ linkage. The structure of cellulose is given in Fig. 1. The present research paper describes the synthesis of CNTAA resin and its use in removal and recovery of heavy metal ions from effluent of Apex Steel Industry, Jodhpur, India.

Results and discussion

FTIR characterization :

The FTIR spectrum of CNTAA resin and Zn loaded resin have been recorded and shown in Figs. 3 and 4. The spectra of polysaccharide are generally observed in

age mesh size and dried carefully in vacuum desiccator. The boat was packed uniformly for analysis. For the dynamic measurement, the system was heated at a constant heating rate of 20 °C per minute under static air atmosphere till the complete decomposition. The CNTAA resin is found to stable up to 401 °C and then the degradation was found to be rapid. The obtained TGA curve of CNTAA resin is shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5. TGA curve of CNTAA resin.

Table 1. The characteristics features of effluent of Apex Steel Industry, Jodhpur, India

Appearance : Turbid; pH : 4.4; Colour : Dirty green; Total hardness : 965

Metal ions	Concentration (ppm)
Fe ^{II}	1.03
Cu ^{II}	0.76
Zn ^{II}	3.16
Pb ^{II}	0.66
Cd ^{II}	0.16
Cr ^{II}	0.72
Ni ^{II}	0.14
Co ^{II}	0.68
Mg ^{II}	19.20
Ca ^{II}	80.00

Other anions (ppm) : fluoride = 0.88; sulphate = 926.12; cyanide = 0.04.

Removal of metal ions from effluent of Apex Steel Industry, Jodhpur, India :

The results of percentage removal of metal ions from effluent of Apex Steel Industry by CNTAA resin are given in Table 3. It reveals that maximum removal percentage for Pb^{II}, Cd^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II} and Fe^{II} were achieved at pH

Table 2. The adsorption % of different metal ions on CNTAA resin (adsorption and desorption)

Metal ions	Adsorption % of different metal ions onto CNTAA resin after 10 cycles				
	0 cycle	2 cycles	4 cycles	8 cycles	10 cycles
Pb ^{II}	74.25	72.57	70.83	70.24	70.32
Cd ^{II}	85.05	82.67	80.73	80.24	80.18
Cu ^{II}	88.54	86.82	83.71	83.17	83.64
Zn ^{II}	93.05	90.63	89.08	89.04	89.10
Fe ^{II}	96.37	93.87	90.76	90.84	90.64

Table 3. Percentage removal of metal ions from industrial effluent by CNTAA resin

pH	Pb ^{II}	Cd ^{II}	Cu ^{II}	Zn ^{II}	Fe ^{II}
2.0	48.23	53.07	62.08	65.55	70.43
3.0	60.42	63.57	67.45	71.34	75.04
4.0	74.25	77.54	80.79	82.58	85.24
5.0	67.48	85.05	88.67	91.57	93.49
6.0	58.65	73.07	83.05	93.05	96.37
7.0	47.37	58.08	66.68	73.43	78.54
8.0	38.86	42.45	56.47	60.54	65.24

ranges 3.0 to 6.0 respectively. It is clear from the reported table that the percentage removal of metal ions first increases and then decreases with increasing pH. It suggests that selectivity of metal ion is dependent on pH.

Distribution coefficient (K_d) of metal ions :

The pH has a strong effect on the distribution coefficient (K_d) of metal ions. The results of distribution coefficient (K_d) of metal ions from effluent of Apex Steel Industry, Jodhpur are given in Table 4. The perusal of the results shows that the distribution coefficient value first increases and then decreases with increasing pH, the optimum results obtained at pH ranges 4 to 6. The ad-

Table 4. Distribution coefficient (K_d) of metal ions from effluent of Apex Steel Industry, Jodhpur

pH	$K_d \times 10^3$				
	Pb ^{II}	Cd ^{II}	Cu ^{II}	Zn ^{II}	Fe ^{II}
2.0	8.857	10.000	16.206	18.987	23.225
3.0	14.444	16.666	20.400	24.757	29.615
4.0	28.823	30.000	40.666	47.280	54.375
5.0	20.000	43.333	74.444	107.377	137.142
6.0	13.571	22.000	48.461	133.200	247.500
7.0	8.857	12.857	27.486	27.486	34.782
8.0	5.000	7.777	15.300	15.034	18.108

sorption of heavy metal ions on CNTAA resin starts when the pH rises to the range where most acidic ion exchange sites start to exchange hydronium ion for metal and the capacity reaches the maximum value in the pH range where all the ion exchange sites take part in the reaction and the functional group is able to form complex with the metal cations²⁹. The decrease in K_d values after the maximum in the neutral and alkaline region can be explained due to fact that the metal ions from stable octahedral complex with CNTAA resin in acidic medium.

Chelating complexes formation by CNTAA resin :

CNTAA resin contains nitrilotriacetic acid functional group, which possesses not only protons that can exchange with cations, but also oxygen atoms that can coordinate directly with metal ions. Therefore, the adsorption ability of CNTAA resin for enriching metal ion may be very strong. The bonds formed in this kind of metal complex have both covalent and ionic characteristics. The adsorption of Fe^{II} and Zn^{II} were found to be higher than other metal ions in the present studies. This is because of the fact that Fe^{II} and Zn^{II} form stable octahedral complex in acidic medium. The probable structure for the complex of CNTTA resin with metal ions is shown in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6. Probable complex structure of CNTAA resin with metal ions.

Quantitative separation of metal ions :

The superior selectivity towards multivalent cations exhibited by chelating resin has been demonstrated in column experiments by using K_d values. The considerable difference in distribution coefficient of the metal ions implies that separation of metal ion from their mixtures would be possible. An ideal situation would be such that one K_d value is greater than the K_d value for other metal ions. The first eluting fraction of hydrochloric acid carries one metal ion which has smaller K_d value. The second metal ion is eluted by changing the hydrochloric acid concentrations. Pb^{II} was eluted with 0.05 N HCl solution at the same condition whereas the other metal ion shows high K_d values. Therefore, other metal ions were eluted

quantitatively with different strength of HCl solutions. The results are reported in Table 5.

Table 5. Quantitative separation of metal ions on a column of CNTAA resin

Metal ions	Amount loaded (mg)	Amount recovery (mg)	Recovery of metal ions (%)	Eluent used (M HCl)	Volume of eluent (ml)
Pb^{II}	0.49	0.45	93.47	0.05	45
Cd^{II}	0.13	0.12	95.08	0.5	50
Cu^{II}	0.67	0.65	97.38	1.0	55
Zn^{II}	2.94	2.94	100.00	1.5	60
Fe^{II}	0.99	0.98	99.67	2.0	80

Effect of agitation speed on removal of metal ions :

The effect of agitation speed on removal of metal ions was studied by varying the speed of agitation from 0 (without shaking) to 200 rpm, while keeping the other parameters optimum. It can be seen from Fig. 7, that the removal of metal ions by CNTAA resin is increased when agitation speed increased from 50 to 120 rpm. These results can be associated to the fact that the increase of the agitation speed, improves the diffusion of metal ions towards the surface of the resin. This also indicates that a shaking rate in the range 100–120 rpm is sufficient to assure that all the surface binding sites are made readily available for metal ions uptake. For convenience, agitation speed of 130 rpm was selected as the optimum speed for CNTAA resin for removal of metal ions from effluent of Apex Steel Industry. This observation is in full agree-

Fig. 7. Effect of agitation speed for removal of metal ions on CNTAA resin.

ment with the published results by Jeon and Park in 2003³⁰,

Effect of treatment time on removal of metal ions :

The results (Fig. 8) of treatment time indicate that removal percentage of metal ions increased with an increase in contact time before equilibrium is reached. It can be seen that removal of metal ions by CNTAA resin is increased when contact time is increased from 30 to

Fig. 8. Effect of changing treatment time on removal percentage of metal ions.

240 min and optimum contact time for CNTAA adsorbent was found to be 240 min. Other parameters such as pH of solution and agitation speed were kept optimum, while temperature was kept at 25 °C. Greater availability of nitrilotriacetic groups on the surface of cellulose which are required for interaction with metal ions, significantly improved the binding capacity and the process proceeded rapidly. This result is important, as equilibrium time is one of the important parameters for an economical treatment of industrial effluent.

Effect of treatment temperature on removal of metal ions :

Fig. 9 shown the effect of treatment temperature on the adsorption percentage of the metal ion on CNTAA resin. The adsorption percentage of metal ion decreases by increasing the treatment temperature from 25 to 75 °C. This observation is in full agreement with the published results by Khalil *et al.* in 1998³¹.

Effect of CNTAA dose on removal of metal ions :

The adsorption of metal ions is significantly influenced by the amount of the CNTAA resin added. The

Fig. 9. Effect of changing treatment temperature on removal percentage of metal ions.

effect of the adsorbent dose on the amount of metal ions removed was studied by the application of varying CNTAA doses. The maximum adsorption by CNTAA resin was achieved with an adsorbent dose of 0.1 g and constant up to 0.2 g. The initial increase adsorption percentage of metal ions was due to the availability of more adsorption sites. On increasing the CNTAA resin concentration further, the adsorption percentage of metal ions constant. This effect might be attributed to overlapping or aggregation of adsorption sites of resin resulting constant of total surface area of the adsorbent. These results are represented in Fig. 10.

Fig. 10. Effect of adsorbent dose on adsorption of metal ions on CNTAA resin.

Effect of flow rate on removal of metal ions :

In the column experiment, the flow rate of the sample solution was an important parameter not only affecting the recovery of metal ions, but also controlling the time of analysis. Therefore, the effect of flow rate on adsorption of metal ions were investigated under the optimum conditions (pH, eluent, etc.) by passing 100 ml of sample solution through the micro column. The flow rates were adjusted in range of 1.0–5.0 ml min⁻¹ controlled by a peristaltic pump. It was found that the optimum flow rate for these metal ions was 3–4 ml min⁻¹ for maximum loading. The flow rates lower than 2.0 ml min⁻¹ was not studied to avoid the long analysis time. However, at a flow rate greater than 4 ml min⁻¹, there was decrease in the metal ion recovery, as the metal ions probably could not equilibrate properly with the resin bed. Thus, a flow rate of 4.0 ml min⁻¹ was selected throughout the column experiment.

Experimental

Effluent of Apex Steel Industry, Jodhpur, India :

The effluent of Apex Steel Industry, Jodhpur, Rajasthan (India) having following characteristic features are summarized in Table 1.

Synthesis of cellulose nitrilotriacetic acid [CNTAA] resin : Synthesis of CNTAA resin accomplished in the following two steps :

Preparation of epoxypropyl ether of cellulose :

32.4 g (0.2 mol) of cellulose powder was taken in round bottom flask and slurried in dioxane. 50% of aqueous solution of sodium hydroxide was added in the flask to make it alkaline, till pH reached to 9.5. The solution was stirred for one hour. 9.25 g (0.1 mol) epichlorohydrin was added dropwise and stirring was continued for 5 h at 60 °C. The product epoxypropyl ether of cellulose was formed and it was used as such for further reaction.

Preparation of cellulose nitrilotriacetic acid resin :

Epoxy propyl ether of cellulose was allowed to react with 19.11 g (0.1 mol) of nitrilotriacetic acid in the alkaline medium and the stirring was continued for another 6 h at 60 °C. The product was filtered under vacuum and washed with 90% methanol, containing few drops of hydrochloric acid to remove inorganic impurities. Finally

it was washed with pure methanol. The product cellulose nitrilotriacetic acid resin was free flowing light brown powder. The yield was 42.07 g. The reaction scheme for synthesis of CNTAA resin is given in Fig. 2.

Resin durability :

The resin durability of the metal ions on the resin was subjected to several loading and elution operations. It was observed that the absorbency of different metal ion on the CNTAA resin after 10 cycles for all the five metal ions varied by less than 2%. The adsorbed metal ions were easily desorbed by treatment of different strength of acids, at room temperature. These results are shown in Table 2.

Determination of ion exchange capacity :

Resin capacity is usually expressed in terms of equivalents per liter (eq/L) of resin or milli equivalents per gram of dry resin. The ion exchange capacity, which is generally taken as a measure of the hydrogen ion liberated by neutral salt to flow through the composite cation exchanger was determined by standard column process. 1.0 g (dry mass) of the composite ion exchange material in H⁺ form was placed in a glass column with a glass wool support at the bottom. It was washed with demineralized water to remove any excess of acid remained sticking on the particles. The hydrogen ions eluted with 0.1 M solution of sodium chloride. The flow rate was kept 4 ml min⁻¹. The collected effluent was titrated against a standard solution of sodium hydroxide using phenolphthalein as an indicator. The hydrogen ions released were then calculated.

Determination of distribution coefficient (K_d) of metal ions :

Distribution coefficient (K_d) is defined as the ratio of the concentration of a given metal ion in the exchanger to the concentration of that metal ion in the solution at equilibrium. The distribution coefficient (K_d) of metal ions was determined by batch method. The pH of solution was adjusted with HCl and NaOH, and maintained by a suitable buffer at desired values : KCl-HCl buffer for pH 2, acetate buffer for pH 3 to 5, phosphate buffer for pH 6 to 8. A sample solution (100 ml) containing a known concentration of the studied metal ion were transferred to a Erlenmeyer flask and after adjusting its pH values, 0.1 g

of the modified resin was added to the solution and the mixture was shaken continuously in a temperature controlled shaker at 25 ± 2 °C for 4 h. The amount of metal ions in the solution before and after equilibration was determined by using AAS. The distribution coefficient (K_d) of metal ions were calculated by the following equation.

$$K_d = [(I - F/F) \times V/M] \text{ ml g}^{-1}$$

where I is the initial amount of the metal ion in solution, F is the final amount of metal ion after equilibrium with resin, V is the volume of metal ion solution (ml) and M is the weight of the resin taken (g).

Determination of removal percentage of metal ions :

The removal percentage of metal ions by CNTAA resin was calculated by using this formula.

$$\%R = [(I - F/I) \times 100]$$

where $\%R$ is removal percentage, I and F are initial and final equilibrium concentrations of metal ion in solution respectively.

Column operation :

The column operation used for analyzed the recovery of metal ion. In the column experiment, a glass tube with 1.6 cm internal diameter and 20 cm height, packed with 9.5 cm of resin (9.0 g) was used. 100 ml of the metal ion solution was passed through the column at a flow rate of 4 ml per minute. The flow rate controlled by a peristaltic pump. The column was washed with distilled water to remove the traces of unadsorbed ions.

Conclusions :

The removal of heavy metal ions by CNTAA resin is now considered one of the most promising technique due to its cost effectiveness, eco-friendliness, and rapidness. The CNTAA resin having useful environmental or commercial application is their ability to bind heavier elements selectively. The adsorbed metal ions on CNTAA resin were effectively eluted by different strength of acid solution and the resin can be regenerate several times.

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